

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF A COARSE GLASS - CEMENT - SAND TERNARY BRICK BLEND

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ABSTRACT

Coarse glass has several applications in various sectors including construction, landscaping and industrial uses. Despite this, sustainability issues in the construction industry has been a major cause for concern in reducing the environmental impact of its operations/activities. However, there is a growing interest in substituting alternative aggregate materials, largely as a potential use for recycled materials. Also, it is still unclear on their importance on the construction outcome, especially in the structural integrity. Hence, this study presents findings from the investigation of the compressive strength characteristics of ternary concrete blend using coarse glass, sand and cement. Sand, cement, coarse glass and water were used as the primary materials for the experiment. Five different samples were prepared at different replacement levels of coarse glass (5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25%), using the ternary blend, with cement and sand forming the control. The major equipment/tools were pyrometer, compression machine, chamber kiln (oven), weighing balance, brick mould, wheel barrow, shovel and hand trowel. Results indicate that the sample G30 has the highest compressive strength (18.69 N/mm²) after curing and crushing while the lowest is G15 (10.52 N/mm²). Furthermore, the results of the experiment indicates that the lightness of the brick samples (2.10 - 2.50 kg) makes it easier to handle, though its use requires typical and logical considerations to maintain strength, durability and avoid disintegration. The findings demonstrate that alternative materials, such as recycled glass, possess considerable compressive strength potential for integration into sustainable construction. However, these practices could play a vital role in advancing sustainable building methods locally and globally.

Keywords: Brick, Compressive Strength, Glass, Ternary blend

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INTRODUCTION

Conventional concrete aggregate consists of sand (fine aggregate) and various sizes and shapes of gravel or stones (coarse aggregate). While there is significant research on many different materials for aggregate substitutes such as granulated coal ash, blast furnace slag or various solid wastes including fiberglass waste materials, granulated plastics, paper and wood products or wastes, sintered sludge

pellets and others, it is still unclear on their importance on the construction outcome, especially in the structural integrity (Shaikh & Islam, 2020).

Recycled waste glasses were used as coarse and fine aggregates replacement in concrete. According to Harrison et al., (2023), coarse aggregates were replaced with green bottles coarse aggregates at third, half, two thirds, and 100% replacement ratios. The replacement of a third coarse aggregate was established as being the most suitable for retaining the properties of the concrete mix design. Also, Patil and Pathak, (2017) opined that waste glass, a component of the global solid waste stream, poses an environmental challenge due to its non-biodegradable nature and the considerable landfill space it occupies. Therefore, repurposing waste glass into coarse glass aggregates provides a solution and also reducing the demand of virgin materials.

Furthermore, glass that has been purposefully broken up into bigger, irregular pieces often referred to as frit is known as coarse glass. Its variable look which can encompass a wide range of colors, forms and sizes and rough texture set this material apart (Vijayakumar et al., 2013). Coarse glass refers to fractured or intentionally crushed glass particles whose nominal size typically ranges from 2 mm up to several centimeters, replacing natural coarse aggregates like gravel or crushed stones in construction materials. Unlike fine glass powders, coarse glass is valued for its structural integrity and permeability when used as an aggregate, filtration medium, or abrasive (Mathews & Roy, 2021). Over the past two decades, interest in coarse glass has grown due to its potential to divert waste from landfills, improve material properties in composites, and offer new functional applications in environmental engineering.

Additionally, coarse glass are glass materials that have a rough texture, uneven surface, or relatively large and visible particles or grains (Islam et al., 2017). Unlike smooth or polished glass, coarse glass is characterized by its gritty appearance and sometimes translucent or opaque quality. This type of glass is often produced through specific manufacturing processes that intentionally leave the surface unfinished or textured. Coarse glass can be found in a variety of applications including construction, decorative arts, landscaping, and industrial uses (Ling & Poon, 2013). Common forms include frosted glass, textured panels, recycled glass aggregate, and glass cullet (crushed recycled glass). The texture can serve both aesthetic and functional purposes, for example, to diffuse light, provide grip, or offer privacy. Depending on its intended use, coarse glass can vary in composition, size, color and texture. Its durability and resistance to weathering also make it suitable for outdoor use in pavements, tiles, and eco-friendly concrete mixes.. This study however aims to investigate the compressive strength of coarse glass blended brick mix.

METHODOLOGY

The brick samples to be fired were prepared, molded while the cubes were left to dry for 24 hours, after which they were removed from their respective molds prior to the day of firing. The major equipment/tools were pyrometer, compression machine, chamber kiln (oven), weighing balance, brick mould, wheel barrow, shovel and hand trowel. For the preparation of the bricks, the coarse glass, sand and cement were measured using the weighing scale, and a percentage of water was also measured at

each stage for each materials replaced at different replacement levels of coarse glass (5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25%) as well. Then after, the materials was mixed together in a head pan and further transferred into the brick mold. The brick mold was hit multiple times for the brick to compact and form properly, after the brick has been formed, it was then removed from the mold, the sample codes (G5 - G25) were inscribed on it and then it was left out to dry before firing.

The day before the firing, the kiln was cleaned and prepped thoroughly ahead of the next day firing. Once the brick samples were arranged into the kiln, refractory bricks with mortar was used to seal the entrance of the kiln, while leaving a gap (spy hole) in the sealed entrance of the sealed kiln. The gap was left to check for the temperature of the kiln on regular intervals. The pre-heating lasted a single hour before firing started, increasing the temperature from 91°C - 125.2°C. The firing began after pre-heating, increasing the temperature of the kiln every hour. There were twenty (20) bricks that were made and fired in total as the firing lasted 8 hours and 20 minutes with the temperature increased from 270.5°C - 803.5°C. The removal of the bricks from the kiln took place 4 days after it was fired. The brick cubes from the wooden mold were immersed inside a drum already filled up with water for curing. The bricks were allowed to cure for 7, 14, 21 & 28 days respectively after which they were taken for crushing.

Mix Proportions for Bricks

A 5% coarse glass replacement concrete mixture was made using cement, sand, coarse glass and water. Cement of 5.7 kg, sand of 5.7 kg and coarse glass of 0.6 kg was measured using the weighing scale and then water of 2.26 kg was measured as well. The materials were mixed together well, all of which was then transferred into an head pan and further transferred into the oiled wooden cube mold. This is then left out to dry. Four samples of this cube was made. The initials G5 was inscribed on the samples. A 10% coarse glass replacement concrete mixture was made using cement of 5.4 kg, sand of 5.4 kg and coarse glass of 1.2 kg which were all measured using the weighing scale, and then water of 2.16 kg was measured as well. Same procedure was repeated as that of G5 brick samples with four samples made as well. The initials G10 was inscribed on the samples.

For the 15% coarse glass replacement concrete mixture, this was made using cement, sand, coarse glass and water. Cement of 5.1 kg, sand of 5.1 kg and coarse glass of 1.8 kg was measured using the weighing scale, and then water of 2 kg was measured. Same procedures above were followed, moulding four samples as well.. The initials G15 was inscribed on the samples. The 20% coarse glass replacement concrete mixture was made using cement of 4.8 kg, sand of 4.8 kg and coarse glass of 2.4 kg, all of which were measured using the weighing scale, and then water of 1.84 kg was measured. Same procedures above were followed as well while the initials G20 was inscribed on the samples. Lastly, the 25% coarse glass replacement concrete mixture was made using cement of 4.5 kg, sand of 4.5 kg and coarse glass of 3 kg and then water of 1.78 kg. The same aforementioned procedure was repeated and four samples were produced as well. The initials G25 was inscribed on the samples. The mix proportions are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Mix Proportions of Brick Samples

Cube	Weight after firing (kg)	Cement (kg)	Sand (kg)	Coarse glass (kg)	Water (kg)
G5	2.10	5.7	5.7	0.6	2.26
G10	2.20	5.4	5.4	1.2	2.16
G15	2.25	5.1	5.1	1.8	2.00
G20	2.30	4.8	4.8	2.4	1.84
G25	2.50	4.5	4.5	3.0	1.78

Source: Field Study, 2024

Compressive Strength Test Formulas

Load = is the force used to crush the cubes during the crushing process as obtained from the crushing machine in Kilo Newton (kN)

$$\text{Compressive Strength} = \frac{\text{Load (N)}}{\text{Brick Area (mm}^2\text{)}}$$

Where; Load is the strength obtained from the cube during the crushing process in kN.

$$\text{Load (N)} = \text{Load (kN)} \times 1000$$

For the Brick Area, the formula is given below:

$$\text{Brick Area (mm}^2\text{)} = \text{Length} \times \text{Breadth}$$

Where; Length = 100 mm; Breadth = 100 mm

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 2 shows the weight and the compressive strength of the bricks after curing days of 7, 14, 21 and 28 as well as after firing. The weights of the bricks were weighed with a weighing scale before being crushed with a compression machine. The different readings from the crushing of the bricks are as follows:

Table 2: Compressive Strength of Brick Samples

Cube	Weight of Fired Sample (kg)	Load (kN)	Brick Area (mm ²)	Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)
G5	2.10	128.57	10,000	12.86
G10	2.20	137.04	10,000	13.70
G15	2.25	105.24	10,000	10.52
G20	2.30	169.94	10,000	17.00
G25	2.50	186.87	10,000	18.69

Source: Field Study, 2024

Furthermore, the figure 1 shows the pictorial presentation of the compressive strength results of the brick samples after crushing. It is very clear that sample G15 has the lowest compressive strength (10.52 N/mm²) while sample G25 has the highest compressive strength (18.69 N/mm²).

Figure 1: Bar chart showing the Compressive Strength of Brick Samples

Source: Field Study, 2024

DISCUSSION

Coarse glass emerged as a really good natural replacement and alternative to granite, offering improved durability and strength when used as a partial replacement in concrete. Recently, scientific investigations in Nigeria have turned to how to make the reuse of waste materials more environmentally friendly and economically viable. Among such materials is coarse waste glass that has been incorporated into cementitious composites. This study measured the impact of such materials on the compressive strength of the composites, which is considered a crucial structural performance parameter. To be able to obtain the mechanical properties of ternary blends where glass is used as a coarse aggregate component, it is very important to understand the interaction of glass with cement and sand at a molecular level. From the findings of this study, the coarse waste glass in bricks contributed to increasing its structural integrity from 10.52 N/mm² - 18.69 N/mm², offering natural density, weather resistance and thermal insulation properties, which aligns with the findings of Harrison et al., (2023).

Its lightness in nature (2.10 - 2.50 kg) makes it easier to handle, though its use requires typical and logical considerations to maintain strength, durability and avoid disintegration. Similarly, the findings of Otunyo and Okechukwu, (2017) showed that concrete cubes with a fine glass replacement of up to 15% resulted in a 37% increase in compressive strength after 7 and 28 days when compared to the control mix. The findings imply that there is a certain level of glass incorporation beyond which the angular particles of crushed glass cannot contribute to the mechanical interlocking sufficiently, thus, leading to the formation of voids that are detrimental to strength.

Furthermore, the quality of care and accuracy put into the preparation of the samples used for this study highlight and emphasize that reliable performance in concrete production depends not only on the quality of materials but also on appropriate batching, compaction and curing practices, which concurs with the findings of Kuri et al. (2023). Also, variations in compressive strength across samples further emphasize the importance of accurate mix design and stringent quality control and aligns with the findings of Ahmad et al., (2022) which states that quality preparation and design of concrete mix has huge impact on its strength outcomes. Aligned with other similar studies, the exploration of incorporating waste glass in cement-based composites reveals that glass particles can affect the mechanical properties through pozzolanic activity and filler effects. The findings of Zeybek et al., (2022) have been found that the compressive strength increases when waste glass is used at 10-20% replacement levels in experimental research as compared to mixtures without glass. This is similar to the findings of this study, where the highest recorded compressive strength of 18.69 N/mm² was at the 25% partial replacement level. However, this is in contrast to the experiment of Saribiyik et al. (2013) which showed that certain proportions of glass powder (8-10% by weight) resulted in significantly higher compressive strength than the control bricks after 28 days of curing. This proves that glass, if properly treated, can serve both as a filler and a binder, thus improving the mechanical stability of brick systems, leading to an increase in the early compressive strength by improving particle packing and decreasing porosity, whereas a high glass content may cause the formation of stress concentration areas and weakening of the bond between the binder and aggregate, thus negatively influencing strength.

Taken together, these studies as well as the findings of this present study have come to a consensus that incorporating waste glass into cement-based mixtures can result in an increase of compressive strength up to a certain limit, after which the performance deteriorates. In the case of bricks, these coarse glass can be chemically reacted with an appropriate sand-cement matrix mixture in order to produce environmentally friendly and reinforced building materials.

CONCLUSION

The study has demonstrated the potential of integrating waste glass as a suitable partial replacement in brick production. The test confirmed that this material when used and produced accurately can provide competitive, durable and sustainable blend in the the production of bricks, without necessarily replacing the core materials such as cement and coarse sand. In conclusion, the findings demonstrate that alternative materials, such as recycled glass, possess considerable potential for integration into sustainable construction. Transforming waste and underutilized resources into functional building products aligns with global sustainability goals, enhances resource efficiency, and offers cost-effective solutions for the construction industry. With continued optimization and long-term performance evaluations, these practices would play a vital role in advancing sustainable building methods locally and globally.

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